

Making behaviour visible: data-based behaviour support in schools. Evidence from 20 experimental single-case studies

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the practical use of Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) as a brief and economical tool for the initial identification of internalising and externalising behavioural difficulties. The SDQ was not evaluated psychometrically; rather, it served as a data-based decision aid to guide the selection of school-based intervention strategies. Twenty experimental single-case studies (children aged 7–15 years, $M = 10$) were conducted. Based on SDQ results, 12 children received behaviourally oriented interventions for externalising problems, and 8 received cognitively based interventions for internalising symptoms. Daily Direct Behaviour Ratings (DBR) were collected across 30 school days. Multilevel modelling revealed significant behavioural improvement from baseline to the first ($B = 10.956$; $p < .001$; Cohen's $d = 1.31$, 95% CI [1.09, 1.53]) as well as second intervention phases ($B = 13.515$; $p < .01$; Cohen's $d = 1.93$, 95% CI [1.69, 2.16]). Nineteen of 20 cases showed moderate to strong effects. Children with internalising problems appeared to derive greater benefit. The results support a structured model integrating SDQ, theory-based planning, and DBR for data-based decision-making in everyday school practice.

KEYWORDS

Data-based decision-making; single-case experimental design; internalising and externalising behaviour; Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ); Direct Behaviour Rating (DBR)

Introduction

Teachers play a pivotal role in the early detection of emotional and behavioural problems among students. However, numerous empirical studies have revealed consistent perceptual biases: While externalising behaviours such as impulsivity and aggression are often overestimated or more readily identified, internalising problems such as anxiety and depression frequently go unnoticed or are underestimated (Bilz 2014; Conley, Marchant, and Caldarella 2014; Splett et al. 2019).

Papandrea and Winefield (2011), in a mixed-methods study with Australian secondary school teachers, found that students exhibiting externalising behaviours were referred for support services significantly more often than those showing internalising symptoms. Although teachers acknowledged the relevance of withdrawn or silent behaviour, they reported feeling insufficiently trained to identify such issues. Similarly, a Norwegian study by Berg-Nielsen et al. (2012) demonstrated that teachers systematically rated internalising problems as less severe than parents did – especially in girls. The quality of the teacher – student relationship further influenced perceptions: Teachers reported more behavioural issues in conflictual relationships, regardless of the child's actual behaviour.

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These patterns were supported by findings from a vignette-based experiment conducted by Splett et al. (2019). While teachers reliably recognised severe behavioural issues, moderate internalising problems were often not considered in need of intervention. Externalising behaviours, in contrast, were consistently perceived as more serious, even at moderate levels of intensity. Zee and Moritz Rudasill (2021) further showed that internalising symptoms were systematically underestimated when accompanied by disruptive behaviour, suggesting that more salient conduct problems can overshadow subtler emotional difficulties. Novice teachers, in particular, were more likely to misinterpret signs of anxiety, indicating that both diagnostic competence and teaching experience significantly shape perception and judgement.

Despite the importance of early identification, many teachers report uncertainty when confronted with challenging behaviours and point to gaps in their training and professional development (Friedman-Krauss et al. 2014). As a result, support measures are often based on personal intuition rather than standardised procedures. Moser Opitz, Silvia, and Labhart (2019) found that individual educational plans, although legally required in many educational systems, are frequently applied in an unsystematic or inconsistent manner. Crucially, a recent longitudinal study by Kvande et al. (2019) failed to detect significantly positive effects of special education services, attributing this lack of impact primarily to the insufficient implementation of evidence-based practices. This finding highlights a disconnect between the intention to provide support and the quality or effectiveness of its actual delivery.

Taken together, the available evidence underscores that perceptual biases in identifying student behaviour are not isolated cases but rather a structural issue in school practice. These biases tend to systematically disadvantage students with internalising difficulties, who remain under-identified and underserved. Therefore, improving systematic diagnostic procedures and implementing evidence-based models of support are essential strategies for addressing this challenge effectively and sustainably.

Effects and mechanisms of school-based interventions

Against the backdrop of the growing demand for systematic and evidence-based support structures, recent research has increasingly focused on the effectiveness and mechanisms of school-based interventions aimed at reducing internalising and externalising behavioural problems. Both behavioural and cognitive-behavioural approaches are considered promising conceptual foundations.

A meta-analysis by Zhang, Wang, and Neitzel (2023), which reviewed 29 randomised controlled trials of school-based cognitive-behavioural therapy programmes, found a moderate effect size ($d = 0.24$) for the reduction of internalising symptoms. Programmes that employed cognitive restructuring and problem-solving training, particularly when delivered by trained professionals at the secondary level, proved especially effective. The key mechanisms of change involved modifying dysfunctional thought patterns and building coping strategies.

For externalising behaviour problems, behavioural management approaches have shown strong potential. Aldabbagh et al. (2024) analysed 31 studies on teacher-implemented interventions. Professional development in classroom management led to an increased use of positive behavioural strategies, improved teacher-student relationships, and a reduction in conflictual interactions. Among students, externalising symptoms significantly decreased, while prosocial behaviour increased slightly. Particularly notable was a moderate reduction in aggressive-oppositional behaviour based on objective measures – an effect that underscores the importance of reinforcement and structured classroom environments.

In addition, a recent study by Lawrence Farmer and Adams (2021) showed that children with emotional and behavioural disorders benefit most from interventions that are embedded within a multi-tiered, positively framed behavioural support system. The close integration of diagnostic assessment and intervention within such a tiered model supports not only behavioural improvement but also the academic and social development potential of students with high support needs.

Overall, these studies demonstrate that both cognitive-behavioural and behaviourally oriented approaches can be effective – provided they are evidence-based, contextually adapted, and well-implemented (Wilson and Lipsey 2007). Differentiation according to the type and severity of the problem, developmental level, and individual support needs remains crucial for the sustainable success of school-based intervention practices.

Multi-tiered support systems and evidence-based practice: starting points for diagnostic and pedagogical tools

The perceptual biases of teachers and the limited effectiveness of unsystematic support strategies – outlined in the previous sections – highlight the urgent need for structured and empirically grounded support for students with emotional and behavioural difficulties. Internationally recognised frameworks such as the Multi-Tiered System of Supports (MTSS), which integrates elements of Response to Intervention (RTI) and School-Wide Positive Behavioural Supports (SWPBS), offer a conceptual model for identifying student needs early and deriving targeted support measures (Bradshaw et al. 2021; Bradshaw, Mitchell, and Leaf 2010; Fairbanks et al. 2007). Central to these approaches is the close integration of diagnostic assessment and intervention, complemented by ongoing progress monitoring.

However, evidence-based special education practice encompasses more than the implementation of established models. As Hillenbrand (2015) emphasises, it involves the deliberate integration of professional expertise with the best available scientific knowledge – tailored to the specific case at hand. This requires access to diagnostic and pedagogical tools that are both scientifically validated and practically applicable, and which can be adapted to individual support needs. Evidence-based practice, therefore, should not be misunderstood as a technocratic procedure, but rather as a reflective orientation towards empirically supported actions in relation to specific educational contexts.

From this perspective, the focus shifts to tools that can support a systematic, tiered approach to educational support within everyday school practice. Three tools that have emerged in the literature as particularly relevant are outlined below: the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ) as a screening instrument, the ‘84 Handlungsmöglichkeiten’ (84 behaviour support strategies) as a theory-based intervention manual, and Direct Behaviour Rating (DBR) as a method for behavioural progress monitoring.

The SDQ (R. Goodman 1997) is a globally established and economical screening tool for identifying emotional and behavioural difficulties in children and adolescents. Numerous studies attest to its psychometric quality, especially regarding its validity in distinguishing between internalising and externalising problems (A. Goodman, Lamping, and Ploubidis 2010). Integrated within a tiered support framework, the SDQ can facilitate early identification of at-risk students without requiring a clinical diagnosis.

While the SDQ is primarily diagnostic, the ‘84 Handlungsmöglichkeiten’ (Hartke et al. 2020) focus on the implementation of individualised pedagogical support strategies. This manual compiles a wide range of interventions grounded in learning theory and cognitive psychology, addressing both externalising and internalising behaviour problems. Many of the included strategies – particularly those based on cognitive-behavioural approaches – are well supported by empirical evidence. For strategies with humanistic or experiential roots, empirical support is more limited, and their classification as evidence-based requires cautious interpretation. Preliminary studies (Voß et al. 2015; Urban and Hartke 2009) suggest that teachers are able to develop and implement effective, tailored support plans using this tool. Beyond Germany, the strategies are actively used in schools across Austria, Switzerland, Luxembourg, and parts of Belgium. Many of them reflect internationally recognised principles of effective classroom management and behaviour support (e.g. Simonsen et al. 2008). Particularly noteworthy is its integrated structure, which combines diagnostic guidance, intervention strategies, and

evaluation procedures into a cyclical model of pedagogical planning – a key characteristic of evidence-based approaches (Hillenbrand 2015).

To evaluate the effectiveness of interventions over time, DBR offers a practical tool that combines systematic behavioural observation with efficient teacher-based ratings (Chafouleas et al. 2013). Teachers assess defined behavioural dimensions – such as task engagement or impulsivity – immediately after instructional periods. DBR has demonstrated reliability, sensitivity to behavioural change, and feasibility within everyday school settings (Johnson et al. 2016; Kilgus et al. 2012). Within an MTSS framework, DBR provides a valuable means for monitoring intervention effects over time and for documenting a student's response to specific support measures. As such, DBR not only maps behavioural trends but also supports evidence-based decision-making in individual cases, helping educators determine whether to maintain or adjust interventions (Casale et al. 2015).

In summary, the three tools presented here can be understood as complementary components of a comprehensive, evidence-based multi-tiered support system. The SDQ supports the early identification of students at risk, the '84 Handlungsmöglichkeiten' guide the selection of empirically grounded pedagogical interventions, and DBR enables systematic monitoring of intervention outcomes. Together, these tools contribute to overcoming diagnostic biases, enhancing professional practice, and implementing individualised educational support within the school setting.

Research question

In light of documented diagnostic biases and the limited effectiveness of unsystematic interventions, the present study investigates whether an evidence-based support approach – consisting of screening (SDQ), targeted intervention planning (84 behaviour support strategies), and systematic progress monitoring (DBR) – leads to measurable behavioural improvements in students with internalising or externalising difficulties in everyday school settings. The aim is to evaluate the effectiveness of this integrated, data-driven procedure within the framework of evidence-based special education practice.

Method

Study design and procedure

The study was conducted within the practicum module (internship semester) of a master's programme in special education. The support offered was operationalised as a tiered, data-driven behavioural intervention programme. Initially, the ten student participants conducted a universal behavioural screening for all students in their internship classes in collaboration with the respective classroom teachers. The screening results were then categorised into internalising or externalising problem behaviours based on an established scoring guide (A. Goodman, Lamping, and Ploubidis 2010) and compared against the instrument's cut-off values (see Table 1 for screening results).

Based on the joint review of the screening data, each student and their supervising teacher selected one child per class with externalising problems to receive behaviourally oriented intervention, and one child with internalising difficulties to receive support via a cognitive-behavioural strategy (in one class, no. 8, no child met the threshold for internalising symptoms, so two students with externalising problems were selected instead).

In the next step, the teacher and student identified four specific behavioural goals for each selected child to be targeted through the intervention. These target behaviours were derived using the 'school assessment of behaviour and development' (SEVE) planning tool (Hartke et al. 2020), based on the '84 Handlungsmöglichkeiten' (84 behaviour support strategies). These four behavioural goals per child then served as the dependent variables and were measured daily throughout the intervention period.

The study followed a multi-treatment single-case experimental design (A – B – C design; see (Jain and Spieß 2012). An overview of the measurement points for each child and phase is provided in

Table 1. Demographic data, SDQ results, and behavioural targets of the sample ($N = 20$).

student	grade	age	gender	SDQ _{ex}	SDQ _{in}	SEVE
1ex	4 (SE)	10;11	m	17***	4	16, 17, 18, 21
1in	4 (SE)	10;11	m	7	14***	18, 19, 37, 44
2ex	2/3 (SE)	9;1	m	15***	5	23, 25, 26, 27
2in	2/3 (SE)	8;4	f	9*	12***	78, 79, 81, 82
3ex	7 (SE)	12;2	m	14***	4	09, 15, 23, 37
3in	7 (SE)	13;1	m	6	9**	18, 36, 44, 48
4ex	2 (SE)	7;4	m	14***	10***	23, 25, 26, 27
4in	2 (SE)	7;2	m	7	11***	50, 53, 54, 55
5ex	2 (PS)	7;11	m	11**	0	17, 23, 25, 27
5in	2 (PS)	7;10	m	11**	17***	31, 53, 54, 78
6ex	10 (SE)	15;5	m	9*	8**	15, 17, 23, 37
6in	10 (SE)	15;6	m	2	17***	19, 64, 78, 89
7ex	2 (SE)	8;5	m	10**	5	23, 25, 26, 28
7in	2 (SE)	9;3	m	17***	14***	16, 20, 21, –
8ex	10 (SE ^a)	15;11	m	11**	5	07, 20, 23, 89
8ex2	8 (SE ^b)	14;7	m	14***	3	07, 49, 55, 56
9ex	3 (SE)	9;2	m	19***	4	23, 25, 27, 29
9in	3 (SE)	10;1	m	17***	17***	37, 38, 43, 44
10ex	4 (HS)	10;0	m	16***	11***	85, 86, 87, 91
10in	4 (HS)	9;0	f	1	12***	15, 16, 20, 21

Notes. SDQ_{ex} = Sum of the Conduct Problems and Hyperactivity scales; SDQ_{in} = Sum of the Peer Problems and Emotional Symptoms scales; * = slightly elevated risk, ** = high risk, *** = very high risk according to A. Goodman, Lamping, and Ploubidis (2010); SEVE = DBR-items based on Hartke et al. (2020); a = intensive support class; PS = primary school; SE = special education school; HS = hospital school.

Table 2. Cumulative descriptive values across all cases.

	n_A	n_B	n_C	mis_A	mis_B	mis_C	$M_A (SD)$	Med_A	$M_B (SD)$	Med_B	$M_C (SD)$	Med_C	NAP_{A-B}	NAP_{A-C}
<i>M</i>	11.9	9.8	10.7	1	0.5	1.4	29.87 (11.96)	27.58	47.62 (14.92)	41.28	56.07 (15.07)	75.13	81.04	86.39
<i>Min</i>	10	8	8	0	0	0	11.25 (3.35)	3.00	26.30 (4.45)	8.00	28.78 (0.00)	45.50	58.13	55.37
<i>Max</i>	14	12	15	4	3	5	47.00 (25.76)	48.00	71.80 (24.89)	76.50	86.83 (32.69)	100.00	98.50	100.00

Notes. n = number of measurement points; mis = number of missing values.

Table 2. During the baseline phase (A), each child's problem behaviour was recorded over 10 to 14 measurement points without implementing any specific intervention. This A-phase served as an individualised baseline reference for each child.

In intervention phase 1 (B), the first support measure was introduced, selected using planning tool II (for externalising problems) or III (for internalising problems) from the '84 Handlungsmöglichkeiten' catalogue (Hartke et al. 2020). The specific measures implemented are shown in Figure 1. Behavioural data collection continued throughout this phase (8 to 12 data points in phase B). In intervention phase 2 (C), a second intervention component from the planning tools was added to the first measure. Continuous behaviour tracking was maintained in this phase as well (8 to 15 measurement points in phase C).

Sample

A summary of the sample characteristics and screening results is provided in Table 1. A total of 20 students (18 boys and 2 girls), aged between 7 years and 2 months and 15 years and 11 months, participated in the study. The majority of the children ($n = 16$) were enrolled in a special school with a focus on emotional and behavioural development. Two students attended an introductory class at a general primary school, and two children (one boy and one girl) were inpatients at a child and adolescent psychiatric clinic during the study period, receiving instruction through the hospital school.

Figure 1. Individual behaviour development Note. Behavioural rating trajectories across all phases for all 20 children, with indication of the intervention strategies used. The line shows the baseline median.

Measurements

Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire

The behavioural screening was conducted using the German teacher version of the SDQ (R. Goodman 1997; Klasen et al. 2003). The SDQ comprises 25 items rated on a 3-point scale from 0 = not true to 2 = certainly true. According to A. Goodman, Lamping, and Ploubidis (2010), the externalising problems score (SDQ-Ex) is calculated by summing the 10 items from the 'Hyperactivity' and 'Conduct Problems' subscales. Similarly, the internalising problems score (SDQ-In) is derived by summing the items from the 'Peer Problems' and 'Emotional Symptoms' subscales. Each score ranges from 0 to 20.

Based on the normative data from A. Goodman, Lamping, and Ploubidis (2010), the following thresholds apply for SDQ-Ex: 7–9 = slightly elevated risk, 10–11 = high risk, 12–20 = very high risk. For SDQ-In, the cut-offs are: 6–7 = slightly elevated, 8–9 = high, 10–20 = very high. Both SDQ-Ex and SDQ-In have demonstrated significantly elevated odds ratios for corresponding DSM-IV clinical diagnoses (A. Goodman, Lamping, and Ploubidis 2010). Thus, the SDQ can be considered a valid instrument for the purpose of this study.

The SDQ is one of the most widely used screening tools worldwide and is available in over 80 languages (Carneiro, Costa, and Leal 2023). The internal consistency of the problem scales ranges between $\alpha = .70$ to $.88$ (R. Goodman 2001). Recent studies further confirm that the combined SDQ scales for externalising and internalising problems demonstrate good convergent and discriminant validity (Carneiro, Costa, and Leal 2023). The SDQ was therefore used as a practical, low-threshold screening instrument to inform data-based allocation to internalising or externalising intervention strategies. While alternative instruments such as the SEVE (Hartke et al. 2020) or the LSL (Petermann and Petermann 2013) were considered, these tools primarily focus on current classroom behaviours or social-emotional skills and, to our knowledge, lack evidence of predictive validity for distinguishing developmental risk types. The SDQ's international comparability, accessibility, and established construct differentiation supported its use in the present study.

It is important to note that the present study did not aim to psychometrically validate the SDQ. Instead, the instrument was used pragmatically as a data-based decision aid to guide the assignment of students to theoretically grounded, school-based intervention strategies.

Direct Behaviour Rating

Behavioural progress was monitored by operationalising specific target behaviours, which were rated immediately after a defined instructional situation. In the present study, DBR was used as a multiple-item scale (MIS): For each child, the four individualised behavioural goals selected from the SEVE (Hartke et al. 2020) were rated on an 11-point scale ranging from 0% (does not apply at all) to 100% (fully applies). According to Casale et al. (2017), a MIS is preferable to a single-item scale (SIS) when measuring intraindividual behavioural change, as it provides greater reliability. For each measurement point, the mean of the four items was calculated as the behavioural score for that day.

The behavioural goals assessed in this study were primarily related to the domain of academic engagement and learning behaviour. For this type of behaviour, the DBR method demonstrates strong reliability coefficients (ϵ^2 und $\phi \geq .80$; Volpe and Briesch 2012).

SEVE – ‘school assessment of behaviour and development’

SEVE (Hartke et al. 2020) is the first of the planning tools included in the 84 evidence-based strategy manual. It comprises 91 items grouped into six developmental domains: (I) behaviour, (II) cognition, (III) language, (IV) motor skills and perception, (V) emotion, and (VI) self-concept, interests, and motivation. Domain I (behaviour) contains 56 items further divided into eight subdomains.

For each child, student teachers and classroom teachers jointly selected four SEVE items to serve as intervention goals, which were then assessed daily using the MIS. Across the 20 single-case interventions, a total of 38 different SEVE items were used (for item-to-case mapping, see Table 1).

Among the 11 children receiving behaviourally oriented interventions for externalising problems, most selected goals were located in the subdomain ‘academic behaviour’ within domain I. The most frequently chosen items were item 23 (‘starts tasks promptly,’ selected 8 times) and item 25 (‘remains focused throughout the activity,’ selected 5 times). For the nine children who received cognitive-behavioural interventions targeting internalising difficulties, selected goals were more broadly distributed across domains. Most frequently selected were item 44 from domain I, subdomain ‘social behaviour’ (‘responds appropriately to minor disappointments’) and item 78 from domain V (‘approaches new tasks or assessments with confidence’), each chosen three times.

Data analysis

To examine the impact of the described support measures (theory-driven interventions based on screening results), multiple analytical methods were applied. First, a descriptive data analysis was conducted, including visual and numerical comparisons across the three phases (A, B, C). In addition, effect sizes were calculated at the single-case level, and inferential statistical analyses were performed across all cases.

For each child, means, standard deviations, and medians were calculated per phase. To quantify the magnitude of behavioural change between phases, the Non-Overlap of All Pairs (NAP) was used as an effect size metric (Alresheed, Hott, and Bano 2013). NAP was computed as follows: all measurement points in the baseline phase (A) were pairwise compared with all points in intervention phase 1 (B). One point was awarded for each pair where the B-phase value exceeded the A-phase value, and 0.5 points for ties. The sum of these points formed the numerator. The total number of possible comparison pairs (number of A points \times number of B points) constituted the denominator. The NAP score was expressed as a percentage (numerator \div denominator \times 100). According to Alresheed, Hott, and Bano (2013), NAP values between 66% and 92% indicate medium effects, while values of 93% or higher reflect strong effects.

A NAP score was also calculated for the comparison between the baseline phase and intervention phase 2 (C), using the same procedure. A NAP of 50% would indicate no change relative to baseline; values below 50% would suggest deterioration.

In addition to single-case analyses, the data from all 20 children were analysed using multilevel regression modelling (Wilbert 2025). Measurement occasions (level 1) were nested within individual students (level 2). A random-intercept, random-slope model was estimated, with phase trend, slope, and level change modelled as fixed effects. For behavioural outcome data, minimal or no trend or slope effects were expected, as behaviour (unlike academic performance) typically does not exhibit natural linear or exponential growth over time. A significantly positive level effect (i.e. a step change between phases) would indicate a systematic effect of the intervention.

All graphical and statistical analyses were conducted using R, applying the *scan* package (Wilbert and Lüke 2016).

Results

Table 2 summarises cumulative descriptive values across all cases, including phase-wise means and NAP values. Table 3 presents descriptive statistics for all 20 individual cases, detailing changes across baseline and both intervention phases. Figure 1 shows the behavioural rating trajectories across all phases for each child, along with an annotation of the specific intervention strategies implemented in phases B and C.

Externalising behaviour problems

For the eleven children exhibiting externalising behavioural problems, the comparison between the baseline phase (A) and the first intervention phase (B) indicated a moderate intervention effect in seven cases. In two children (2_ex and 10_ex), the data suggested a strong effect. In the remaining two cases (5_ex and 8_ex), no meaningful behavioural change was observed between the baseline and the first intervention phase. However, all Non-Overlap of All Pairs (NAP) values exceeded 50%, indicating that no deterioration occurred in either case. Across the externalising subsample, NAP values for Phase A vs. B ranged from 58% to 99%.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of all 20 individual cases.

student	n_A	n_B	n_C	mis_A	mis_B	mis_C	$M_A (SD)$	Med_A	$M_B (SD)$	Med_B	$M_C (SD)$	Med_C	NAP_{A-B}	NAP_{A-C}
1ex	10	10	10	0	0	0	45.70 (20.35)	41.50	69.40 (17.79)	69.00	74.70 (19.00)	84.00	86.50	85.50
1in	10	10	10	0	0	0	33.80 (4.71)	33.00	38.30 (5.17)	39.00	46.60 (4.74)	45.50	75.50	97.00
2ex	13	11	15	3	1	3	23.60 (9.54)	25.00	71.80 (16.34)	76.50	86.83 (8.07)	89.00	98.50	100.00
2in	13	12	15	4	2	5	16.67 (3.35)	15.00	26.30 (4.50)	25.00	54.60 (13.15)	59.00	96.67	100.00
3ex	12	9	9	0	0	0	34.83 (12.26)	33.00	43.56 (14.37)	43.00	62.22 (21.14)	60.00	72.69	86.11
3in	12	9	9	0	0	0	43.75 (5.10)	44.00	69.11 (10.30)	73.00	63.56 (22.09)	70.00	98.15	77.78
4ex	14	11	10	3	1	0	31.36 (25.76)	20.00	61.90 (15.64)	59.00	44.10 (12.31)	49.00	84.09	77.27
4in	14	12	11	4	1	0	24.90 (5.24)	26.50	32.73 (4.45)	33.00	65.18 (11.94)	68.00	87.27	100.00
5ex	11	9	10	0	0	0	45.91 (12.85)	48.00	54.33 (24.89)	58.00	69.20 (20.14)	75.50	60.61	81.82
5in	12	8	10	0	0	0	32.25 (8.69)	33.00	56.75 (22.58)	53.00	74.80 (15.40)	76.50	84.90	99.58
6ex	10	10	10	0	0	0	47.00 (10.17)	47.50	62.40 (17.27)	38.00	63.50 (9.62)	93.00	80.50	88.00
6in	10	10	10	0	0	5	19.20 (6.49)	16.50	39.70 (16.60)	28.00	46.80 (12.26)	53.00	85.50	98.00
7ex	13	12	10	0	3	1	20.23 (19.95)	13.00	58.33 (13.65)	40.00	70.56 (17.79)	100.00	90.17	94.87
7in	14	9	12	2	1	2	11.25 (19.26)	3.00	29.25 (15.73)	20.00	28.78 (15.12)	68.00	83.33	83.33
8ex	11	8	12	1	0	1	24.30 (17.65)	19.00	29.00 (17.80)	28.00	38.73 (15.84)	93.00	58.13	74.09
8ex2	13	8	12	2	0	1	37.09 (15.94)	35.00	48.62 (21.19)	50.00	39.82 (11.11)	90.00	68.18	55.37
9ex	12	8	10	0	0	0	22.17 (13.11)	20.00	37.75 (18.23)	35.00	50.80 (22.48)	58.00	75.52	83.33
9in	12	8	10	0	0	0	35.75 (13.28)	35.50	38.75 (11.26)	25.00	56.90 (16.5)	85.00	61.98	83.33
10ex	11	11	8	0	0	0	20.55 (10.65)	18.00	43.82 (17.82)	8.00	38.62 (32.69)	88.00	92.56	62.50
10in	11	10	10	0	0	10	27.00 (4.92)	25.00	40.60 (12.76)	25.00	45.00 (0.00)	98.00	80.00	–

Notes. n = number of measurement points; mis = number of missing values.

When comparing the baseline with the second intervention phase (C), eight of the eleven children demonstrated a moderate effect, while two (2_ex and 7_ex) showed a strong intervention effect. In one case (8_ex), no measurable change was found. NAP values for Phase A vs. C in the externalising group ranged from 55% to 100%.

Internalising behaviour problems

For the nine children presenting with internalising difficulties, the comparison between the baseline phase (A) and the first intervention phase (B) yielded NAP values ranging from 62% to 98%. Two children (2_in and 3_in) exhibited strong intervention effects, while seven demonstrated moderate effects. One adolescent (9_in) narrowly missed the commonly accepted significance threshold of 66%, with a NAP score of 62%.

The second intervention phase (C) led to further behavioural improvements in most participants. Three children (3_in, 7_in, and 9_in) achieved moderate effects, with NAP values ranging from 78% to 83%. A strong additional intervention effect was observed in four boys and one girl, with NAP values between 97% and 100%. One pupil (10_in) dropped out of the study at the beginning of phase C due to leaving the clinical school; therefore, no data are available for this phase in their case.

Table 4. Fixed effects of multilevel pairwise regression.

Parameter	B	SE	t	p
Intercept	26.389	3.231	8.168	<.001
Trend	0.528	0.292	1.809	.071
Level B	10.956	3.214	3.409	<.001
Level C	13.515	5.160	2.619	<.010
Slope B	0.222	0.499	0.444	.657
Slope C	0.398	0.478	0.832	.406

Multilevel analysis of intervention effects

The fixed effects model results are summarised in Table 4. The multilevel regression analysis confirmed the findings from the single-case level across the full sample. The intercept differed significantly from zero ($B = 26.389$; 95% CI [20.056; 32.722]; $p < .001$), indicating that behavioural scores during the baseline phase were clearly above the minimum of the measurement scale. A floor effect can therefore be ruled out. Neither a linear time trend nor a phase-specific change in slope reached statistical significance, suggesting high behavioural stability during the non-intervention phases and the absence of spontaneous improvements prior to the onset of the intervention.

In contrast, marked level changes were observed following the interventions. The transition from the baseline to the first intervention phase was associated with a statistically significant improvement in target behaviour ($B = 10.956$; 95% CI [4.657; 17.255]; $p < .001$). Similarly, a significant level increase was found between baseline and the second intervention ($B = 13.515$; 95% CI [3.401; 23.629]; $p < .001$).

To facilitate comparison with existing empirical evidence, standardised effect sizes were calculated: The contrast between baseline and the first intervention phase yielded a large effect (Cohen's $d = 1.31$; 95% CI [1.09; 1.53]), while the contrast between baseline and the second intervention phase showed a very large effect (Cohen's $d = 1.93$; 95% CI [1.69; 2.16]).

This pattern aligns with the theoretical structure of piecewise linear regression models, in which each phase is characterised by a separate intercept and slope. In this study, changes primarily occurred at the phase transitions ('*break points*'), suggesting that the interventions triggered immediate shifts in behavioural levels rather than gradual improvements over time. The non-significant slope parameters further support the interpretation that the observed effects represent abrupt phase-dependent level changes rather than intra-phase trends. Such constellations are typical of interventions that produce direct, phase-specific effects and are ideally modelled using multivariate piecewise regression procedures (Wilbert 2025).

Discussion

The present findings demonstrate that the combined approach – comprising initial screening using the SDQ, theory-driven intervention planning based on the '84 Handlungsmöglichkeiten', and continuous behavioural monitoring via DBR – led to notable improvements in student behaviour across the sample. Both children with externalising and those with internalising behavioural difficulties benefited from the implemented measures, thus supporting the research question affirmatively.

Behavioural ratings improved markedly in 19 out of 20 students during the course of the interventions. Notably, the addition of a second, phase-specific support measure in Phase C yielded further behavioural gains in many cases, exceeding the effects observed during the first intervention phase. These findings suggest that an economically structured, data-based diagnostic and intervention model can enable effective, individualised support without requiring complex or time-consuming diagnostic procedures.

Interestingly, the subgroup of children with internalising difficulties appeared to benefit slightly more from the interventions than their peers with externalising behaviours. In Phase C, five of the

eight internalising cases showed strong effects, whereas only two of the eleven children with externalising problems achieved similarly large behavioural improvements. One possible explanation is that externalising behaviours were already substantially reduced during Phase B, leaving less room for further behavioural gains in Phase C. In contrast, for children with internalising problems, the initial intervention may have been insufficient to fully address their needs, while the second intervention facilitated a more decisive breakthrough.

Taken together, the results support the effectiveness of the selected multi-tiered approach: when the initial intervention did not yield sufficient effects, the addition of a second support strategy often led to further improvements, highlighting the value of flexible, phase-wise enhancement of behavioural support plans.

Substantive implications

The findings of this study underscore the importance of a systematic, data-driven approach to behavioural challenges in school settings. In particular, they align with international research on the differential effectiveness of behaviourally versus cognitively oriented interventions. For externalising behaviour, prior studies (e.g. Aldabbagh et al. 2024; Lawrence; Farmer and Adams 2021) have shown that structured behavioural strategies – such as reinforcement systems, clear expectations, and relationship-building – lead to measurable improvements. Our results support this: behaviourally grounded interventions produced consistent gains among children with externalising difficulties.

In contrast, for internalising problems, cognitive-behavioural interventions – such as self-instruction and coping strategies – are recommended in the literature (e.g. Zhang, Wang, and Neitzel 2023). and were found effective in our study as well. Particularly in Phase C, adjusted cognitive strategies led to marked improvements in students who had not sufficiently responded to the first intervention. These results reinforce the practical utility of distinguishing between internalising and externalising patterns—e.g. via the SDQ – as a diagnostic basis for selecting theoretically sound support strategies.

The data further highlight the importance of continuous behavioural progress monitoring through DBR. Daily ratings enabled early identification of non-response, making it possible to flexibly implement alternative or supplementary interventions in Phase C. This adaptive procedure – comparable to the logic of RTI, SWPBS or MTSS – proved effective in two out of three cases with insufficient initial progress.

Our findings also emphasise the need for individualisation and participatory planning. In cases where students initially rejected interventions, involving them in decision-making processes increased both acceptance and effectiveness. This participatory adjustment should be systematically embedded in school-based support practice. Notably, all interventions in this study were delivered by student teachers during field placements, under professional supervision. This points to the approach's practicability and scalability even for novice practitioners.

Against the background of the diagnostic and implementation challenges described in the introduction (e.g. Bilz 2014; Kvande et al. 2019; Splett et al. 2019), our study demonstrates that structured tools such as the SDQ, DBR, and the '84 Handlungsmöglichkeiten' offer a feasible and efficient way to support students with behavioural needs. When used in combination, they enable targeted, evidence-informed, and child-centred behaviour support – without placing excessive demands on everyday teaching practice.

Methodological limitations

Despite the overall promising results, the present study has several methodological limitations. First, it employed a non-randomised single-case design without a control group. While the applied A – B – C design – with clearly defined phase transitions and the systematic introduction of interventions –

supports a certain degree of internal validity and allows for cautious causal inference, no comparison with untreated groups was undertaken. Moreover, no systematic follow-up data were collected, leaving the long-term stability of the observed behavioural changes unknown.

Second, behavioural development was assessed exclusively by the teaching staff or practicum students using DBR. Although the standardised DBR format, the clearly defined target behaviours, and the high frequency of measurement help promote objectivity and sensitivity in data collection (e.g. Chafouleas et al. 2013; Johnson et al. 2016), expectancy or relationship biases cannot be ruled out. No ratings by independent observers or more objective behavioural indicators were collected; such triangulation would be desirable in future studies to validate effects.

Third, a limitation concerns the composition of the sample: most children were already enrolled in special education settings. As such, the generalisability of findings to students in inclusive classrooms or other school types is limited. That said, the sample size of $N = 20$ is relatively large for single-case research – especially when compared to previous studies with $n < 10$ —and, according to Hillenbrand (Hillenbrand 2015), fulfils the criteria for theory-driven and systematically analysed single-case studies. Nevertheless, the sample was not drawn randomly or systematically but emerged from practical availability within school contexts. Thus, statistical representativeness cannot be assumed.

A further key methodological aspect concerns the analysis of the single-case data. Based on the recommendations of Kratochwill et al. (2010), we adopted a combination of visual data inspection and quantitative analysis. The NAP index (e.g. Parker and Vannest 2009) was chosen to provide an intuitively interpretable measure of individual effects. This was complemented by a multivariate multilevel model to estimate phase-overarching changes, as recommended by Alresheed, Hott, and Bano (2013) for aggregated single-case data. The theoretical reference to piecewise linear regression (Wilbert 2025) further enabled a nuanced distinction between level shifts and slope/trend changes, thereby enhancing the interpretative power of the model.

Despite these limitations, the results yielded a consistent overall picture: the statistically verified level shifts are clearly reflected in the behavioural time series and support the robustness of the main intervention effects.

Practical implications for educational settings

This study yields several practical implications for everyday school practice. First, it demonstrates that teachers can be empowered to identify problematic behaviour early and respond in an evidence-based manner using a relatively simple and time-efficient framework. The SDQ, which is freely available and quick to administer, can offer teachers an initial indication of whether a child's difficulties are primarily internalising or externalising in nature. Based on this classification, the '84 Handlungsmöglichkeiten' (84 behaviour support strategies) provide a practice-oriented resource to select suitable, theory-driven interventions from a broader set of options. This structured catalogue can be particularly valuable for less experienced teachers or special educators seeking reliable guidance.

It is essential that the intervention selection process is data-informed – as in this study, based on the initial SDQ screening – and that its effectiveness is continuously monitored via DBR. Such ongoing progress monitoring provides rapid feedback on success or failure and enables timely adjustments. Schools could implement this model within their existing support structures, e.g. in school-based intervention teams or counselling frameworks, to ensure systematic responses to behavioural challenges.

Second, our findings reiterate the importance of involving the affected students directly. In practice, support goals and measures should be negotiated with the child (and, where appropriate, with their parents). This significantly increases acceptance and engagement. As illustrated in our cases, there should always be an alternative plan available in the event that an initial intervention

does not yield the desired outcome. In such instances, revisiting the intervention catalogue can help identify more suitable alternatives.

Finally, it must be acknowledged that a small percentage of children – approximately 5% in our sample – did not show sufficient progress despite receiving two evidence-based interventions. For these ‘non-responders’, schools should have access to more in-depth diagnostic procedures and tier-three interventions, such as support from school psychologists or therapeutic services. The model presented in this study may help identify such cases: if no measurable progress is observed despite the implementation of two well-established interventions, this should be interpreted as a strong indicator for extended support needs.

In summary, the study offers practice-relevant insights into how teachers can use data to manage behavioural difficulties in everyday school contexts. A simple screening tool like the SDQ, combined with a structured selection and evaluation of support measures, enables effective intervention for both externalising and internalising problems. Key components of successful implementation include a systematic approach, flexibility in adapting strategies, and active collaboration with the students concerned. Targeted professional development and structured support for teachers would be valuable to help translate these research-based practices into routine educational settings.

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Data collection was conducted in compliance with the guidelines of the Swiss Society of Psychology and the Federal Ethical Principles for Research on Human Beings in Switzerland. All legal guardians of participating students received comprehensive information about the objectives, procedures, and scope of the study. Written informed consent was obtained for each participant.

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References

- Aldabbagh, R., C. Glazebrook, K. Sayal, and D. Daley. 2024. "Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of the Effectiveness of Teacher Delivered Interventions for Externalizing Behaviors." *Journal of Behavioral Education* 33 (2): 233–274. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10864-022-09491-4>.
- Alresheed, F., B. L. Hott, and C. Bano. 2013. "Single Subject Research: A Synthesis of Analytic Methods." *Journal of Special Education Apprenticeship* 2 (1). <https://doi.org/10.58729/2167-3454.1015>.
- Berg-Nielsen, T. S., E. Solheim, J. Belsky, and L. Wichstrom. 2012. "Preschoolers' Psychosocial Problems: In the Eyes of the Beholder? Adding Teacher Characteristics as Determinants of Discrepant Parent-Teacher Reports." *Child Psychiatry and Human Development* 43 (3): 393–413. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10578-011-0271-0>.
- Bilz, L. 2014. "Werden Ängste und depressive Symptome bei Kindern und Jugendlichen in der Schule Übersehen?" *Zeitschrift für Pädagogische Psychologie* 28 (1–2): 57–62. <https://doi.org/10.1024/1010-0652/a000118>.
- Bradshaw, C. P., M. M. Mitchell, and P. J. Leaf. 2010. "Examining the Effects of Schoolwide Positive Behavioral Interventions and Supports on Student Outcomes: Results from a Randomized Controlled Effectiveness Trial in Elementary Schools." *Journal of Positive Behavior Interventions* 12 (3): 133–148. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1098300709334798>.
- Bradshaw, C. P., E. T. Pas, K. J. Debnam, and S. Lindstrom Johnson. 2021. "A Randomized Controlled Trial of MTSS-B in High Schools: Improving Classroom Management to Prevent EBDs." *Remedial and Special Education* 42 (1): 44–59. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0741932520966727>.
- Carneiro, F. A., P. A. Costa, and I. Leal. 2023. "Construct-Related Validity of the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaires with Three and Five Dimensions: A Multitrait-Multimethod Analysis." *Clinical Child Psychology and Psychiatry* 28 (4): 1595–1611. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13591045231168703>.
- Casale, G., M. Grosche, R. J. Volpe, and T. Hennemann. 2017. "Zuverlässigkeit Von Verhaltensverlaufsdagnostik über Rater und Messzeitpunkte bei Schülern mit externalisierenden Verhaltensproblemen." *Empirische Sonderpädagogik* 9 (2): 143–164.
- Casale, G., T. Hennemann, R. J. Volpe, A. M. Briesch, and M. Grosche. 2015. "Generalisierbarkeit und Zuverlässigkeit von Direkten Verhaltensbeurteilungen des Lern- und Arbeitsverhaltens in Einer Inklusiven Grundschulklasse." *Empirische Sonderpädagogik* 7 (3): 258–268.
- Chafouleas, S. M., S. P. Kilgus, T. C. R.-T. Rose Jaffery, M. Welsh, and T. J. Christ. 2013. "Direct Behavior Rating as a School-Based Behavior Screener for Elementary and Middle Grades." *Journal of School Psychology* 51 (3): 367–385. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2013.04.002>.
- Conley, L., M. Marchant, and P. Caldarella. 2014. "A Comparison of Teacher Perceptions and Research-Based Categories of Student Behavior Difficulties." *Education* 134:439–451.
- Fairbanks, S., G. Sugai, D. Guardino, and M. Lathrop. 2007. "Response to Intervention: Examining Classroom Behavior Support in Second Grade." *Exceptional Children* 73 (3): 288–310. <https://doi.org/10.1177/001440290707300302>.
- Farmer, L. G., and D. Adams. 2021. "Social-Emotional Competence Among Students With Special Needs: Relationship Between Foundational and Applied SEL Skills." *American Journal of Educational Research* 9 (7): 410–416. <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-9-7-3>.
- Friedman-Krauss, A. H., C. Cybele Raver, J. M. Neuspiel, and J. Kinsel. 2014. "Child Behavior Problems, Teacher Executive Functions, and Teacher Stress in Head Start Classrooms." *Early Education & Development* 25 (5): 681–702. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10409289.2013.825190>.
- Goodman, A., D. L. Lamping, and G. B. Ploubidis. 2010. "When to Use Broader Internalising and Externalising Subscales Instead of the Hypothesised Five Subscales on the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ): Data from British Parents, Teachers and Children." *Journal of Abnormal Child Psychology* 38 (8): 1179–1191. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10802-010-9434-x>.
- Goodman, R. 1997. "The Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire: A Research Note." *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry* 38 (5): 581–586. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-7610.1997.tb01545.x>.
- Goodman, R. 2001. "Psychometric Properties of the Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire." *Journal of the American Academy of Child and Adolescent Psychiatry* 40 (11): 1337–1345. <https://doi.org/10.1097/00004583-200111000-00015>.
- Hartke, B., Y. Blumenthal, O. Carnein, and R. Vrban. 2020. *Schwierige Schüler - Förderschule: 84 Handlungsmöglichkeiten Bei Verhaltensauffälligkeiten Und Sonderpädagogischem Förderbedarf*. 3 Auflage ed. Bergedorfer Grundsteine Schulltag. Persen.
- Hillenbrand, C. 2015. "Evidenzbasierung Sonderpädagogischer Praxis. Widerspruch oder Gelingensbedingung?" *Zeitschrift für Heilpädagogik* 66 (7).
- Jain, A., and R. Spieß. 2012. "Versuchspläne Der Experimentellen Einzelfallforschung." *Empirische Sonderpädagogik* 4 (3/4): 211–245. <https://doi.org/10.25656/01:9300>.
- Johnson, A. H., F. G. Miller, S. M. Chafouleas, M. E. Welsh, T. Chris Riley-Tillman, and G. Fabiano. 2016. "Evaluating the Technical Adequacy of DBR-SIS in Tri-Annual Behavioral Screening: A Multisite Investigation." *Journal of School Psychology* 54 (February): 39–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2015.10.001>.

- Kilgus, S. P., S. M. Chafouleas, T. Chris Riley-Tillman, and M. E. Welsh. 2012. "Direct Behavior Rating Scales as Screeners: A Preliminary Investigation of Diagnostic Accuracy in Elementary School." *School Psychology Quarterly* 27 (1): 41–50. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0027150>.
- Klasen, H., W. Woerner, A. Rothenberger, and R. Goodman. 2003. "Die Deutsche Fassung Des Strengths and Difficulties Questionnaire (SDQ-Deu) - Übersicht Und Bewertung Erster Validierungs- Und Normierungsbefunde." <https://doi.org/10.23668/PSYCHARCHIVES.11726>.
- Kratochwill, T. R., J. Hitchcock, and R. H. Horner. 2010. "What Works Clearinghouse Single-Case Design Technical Documentation." Works Clearinghouse Website. http://ies.ed.gov/ncee/wwc/pdf/wwc_scd.pdf.
- Kvande, M. N., O. Bjørklund, S. Lydersen, J. Belsky, and L. Wichstrøm. 2019. "Effects of Special Education on Academic Achievement and Task Motivation: A Propensity-Score and Fixed-Effects Approach." *European Journal of Special Needs Education* 34 (4): 409–423. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08856257.2018.1533095>.
- Moser Opitz, E., P. M. Silvia, and D. Labhart. 2019. "Förderpläne: Instrument Zur Förderung Oder "Bürokratisches Mittel"? Eine Empirische Untersuchung Zum Einsatz Von Förderplänen." *Empirische Sonderpädagogik* 11 (3): 210–224. <https://doi.org/10.25656/01:17780>.
- Papandrea, K., and H. Winefield. 2011. "It's Not Just the Squeaky Wheels That Need the Oil: Examining Teachers' Views on the Disparity Between Referral Rates for Students with Internalizing Versus Externalizing Problems." *School Mental Health* 3 (4): 222–235. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12310-011-9063-8>.
- Parker, R. I., and K. Vannest. 2009. "An Improved Effect Size for Single-Case Research: Nonoverlap of All Pairs." *Behavior Therapy* 40 (4): 357–367. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.beth.2008.10.006>.
- Petermann, U., and F. Petermann. 2013. *LSL. Lehrereinschätzliste Für Sozial- Und Lernverhalten*. 2nd ed. Göttingen: Überarbeitete Hogrefe.
- Simonsen, B., S. Fairbanks, A. Briesch, D. Myers, and G. Sugai. 2008. "Evidence-Based Practices in Classroom Management: Considerations for Research to Practice." *Education & Treatment of Children* 31 (3): 351–380. <https://doi.org/10.1353/etc.0.0007>.
- Splett, J. W., M. Garzona, N. Gibson, D. Wojtalewicz, A. Raborn, and W. M. Reinke. 2019. "Teacher Recognition, Concern, and Referral of Children's Internalizing and Externalizing Behavior Problems." *School Mental Health* 11 (2): 228–239. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12310-018-09303-z>.
- Volpe, R. J., and A. M. Briesch. 2012. "Generalizability and Dependability of Single-Item and Multiple-Item Direct Behavior Rating Scales for Engagement and Disruptive Behavior." *School Psychology Review* 41 (3): 246–261. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02796015.2012.12087506>.
- Voß, S., K. Mahlau, S. Sikora, Y. Blumenthal, K. Diehl, and B. Hartke. 2015. *Evaluationsergebnisse Des Projekts „Rügener Inklusionsmodell (RIM) – Präventive Und Integrative Schule Auf Rügen (PISaR)“ Nach Vier Schuljahren Zum Messzeitpunkt Juli 2014*. Universität Rostock. https://www.rim.uni-rostock.de/storages/uni-rostock/Alle_PHF/RIM/Downloads/RIM-Evaluationsbericht-MZP5_Internet.pdf.
- Vrban, R., and B. Hartke. 2009. "Schwierige Schüler - 49 Handlungsmöglichkeiten Bei Verhaltensauffälligkeiten" Ergebnisse Eines Forschungsvorhabens Zur Entwicklung und Evaluation Von Planungshilfen Zur Unterstützung Des Lehrerhandelns." *Zeitschrift für Heilpädagogik* 60 (2): 54–63.
- Wilbert, J. 2025. *Analyzing Single-Case Data with R and Scan* (Zenodo), ahead of print. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14950444>.
- Wilbert, J., and T. Lüke. 2016. *Single-Case Data Analyses for Single and Multiple AB Designs*. Released. <https://r-forge-project.org/projects/scan>.
- Wilson, S. J., and M. W. Lipsey. 2007. "School-Based Interventions for Aggressive and Disruptive Behavior." *American Journal of Preventive Medicine* 33 (2): 130–143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.amepre.2007.04.011>.
- Zee, M., and K. Moritz Rudasill. 2021. "Catching Sight of Children with Internalizing Symptoms in Upper Elementary Classrooms." *Journal of School Psychology* 87 (August): 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsp.2021.05.002>.
- Zhang, Q., J. Wang, and A. Neitzel. 2023. "School-Based Mental Health Interventions Targeting Depression or Anxiety: A Meta-Analysis of Rigorous Randomized Controlled Trials for School-Aged Children and Adolescents." *Journal of Youth & Adolescence* 52 (1): 195–217. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10964-022-01684-4>.